

PEDAGOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF TEACHING CHEMISTRY IN IMPROVING THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the development of higher education by solving the pedagogical problem, its perspectives and the professional preparation of the student, together with the analysis of the teaching of chemistry as its direction, the identification of priorities in our research, the main directions of its implementation and It is explained about the possibility of defining approaches.

Key words: technological development, chemistry, vocational training, pedagogical problem, integrative approach

The most important thing to achieve the modern quality of professional training of a chemistry teacher is the quality of education and its effectiveness. In addition, we consider the quality and efficiency of education to be interrelated and mutually determining directions of its modernization. By effective, we mean teaching that achieves the highest educational result, that is, achieves the modern quality of education, with the least expenditure of teaching time, efforts of subjects of the educational process, and material and technical resources. At the same time, we attach an important role to its rationalization in achieving educational efficiency, the theoretical and methodological foundations of which were developed in the researches of SAGerus, NE Kuznetsova, etc. developed. At the same time, we consider its technology as the most promising direction of

education rationalization in the context of an integrative approach.

In a general sense, "quality of education" is understood as " a philosophical category and a pedagogical problem from the point of view of calitology - a triple science that includes the theory of quality, the theory of quality assessment (qualimetry) and the theory of educational quality assessment" [353, p. 19]. At the same time, the concept of "quality" is considered as a universal criterion for evaluating the state of an educational institution, that is, the level of creating conditions for educating a well-rounded and versatile person.

The main issue in the development of the problem of educational quality is the issue of the content of this concept. In the concept of modernization of education, the quality of school education is focused on cultural traditions, values and needs of society, social adjustment, independent life choice, training of a developed person through continuous education, including self-education. related to Formation of such a person, according to the developers of the concept, ensures that schoolchildren acquire basic competencies by mastering the system of universal knowledge and skills, mastering the experience of independent activity and responsibility. On the other hand, the quality of higher professional education means the training of a competent, competitive specialist who has mastered his profession perfectly, is ready for effective work, professional growth, social and professional mobility.

It should be noted that the condition of achieving the quality defined in the concept of modernization of education recognizes the need to improve the professional skills of the teacher. That is why the main task of higher pedagogical education has become the task of training highly qualified specialists. Methodical training cannot be left out of its solution, which allows to connect its modern quality with the increase of professional skills of the future chemistry teacher.

In general, supporting the listed characteristics of the personality of a school and university graduate , we believe that the public result of school education is the graduate's functional literacy and moral maturity (VN

Maksimova, etc.), and competence is the result of higher education. We believe that it should be.

Among these directions, we study and implement the connection of methodical courses in specialist training with courses in philosophical-methodical, psycho-pedagogical, chemical and other blocks . Thus, interdisciplinary relations between *the chemistry teaching methodology course and the philosophical and methodological preparation courses are carried out.*

society and education humanization processes , as well as integration , ecologization , rationalization and others of processes essence with introduction ;

of methodology scientific and education in knowledge held place _ about imaginations formation ; to teach Methodical approaches , their essence and chemistry science by developing teaching process organize reach and in management place about ;

to develop ideas about the similarities and differences between science and the subject of study , the logic and methods of scientific and educational knowledge;

chemical and methodological interpretation of the dialectical method of knowledge, its role in the development of the student's personality;

substantiation of the ideological function of chemistry education, the role of knowledge and ideas related to chemistry in mastering the chemical landscape of nature by schoolchildren;

and another cases self organize reach skills formation _

Chemistry study _ methodology course and pedagogical preparation of sciences interdisciplinary connections the following cases done is increased :

chemistry pedagogy of science one network i as teaching methodology about imaginations formation ; research methods with get to know

chemistry of the teacher pedagogical of activity essence and types , pedagogical of his creation nature , chemistry of the teacher duties and professional skill with introduction ;

of students national education development priority directions , it organize of

reaching leader approaches about ideas development ;

of students teaching types and types , their essence , advantages and disadvantages and them eliminate reach ways about knowledge generalization and development ;

open managed pedagogical system as chemistry developing teaching , his basis as problem-integrative teaching about ideas formation ;

school and higher study _ in their countries chemistry science by developing teaching forms , methods and tools with introduce the person to value directed educate ;

chemical education content , it choose , build and systematization principles about imaginations formation ;

chemistry science by developing teaching the results control to do forms , types and methods with get to know and *another cases* .

Chemistry teaching methodology course and psychological preparation of sciences interdisciplinary connections the following with done is increased :

modern chemistry of his teacher professional skills in raising psychological of preparation role open to give

chemistry teaching in the methodology applied psychological research methods with get to know

of teaching the most important methodical approaches essence seeing exit (individually _ differentiate and others) ;

chemistry of teaching developing and problem-integrative types according to students knowledge deepening ;

chemistry science developing study _ conditions school students of the person leader fields development mechanisms and tools justification ;

chemistry in their classes integrative problematic situations create , issues to put and of solving psychological basics with get to know

and another cases school students activities organize achieve , manage , activate and of encouragement psychological the basics open to give and to them

to value directed education _

Chemistry teaching methodology course and chemical preparation of sciences interdisciplinary in communications done is increased .

chemistry of science student identity in development role open to give chemistry science as a science study _ methodology formation and development of chemists added contribution with introduction ;

chemistry science by developing in teaching done being increased to know tools with experience and another methods with introduce them _ use basics ;

Chemical to knowledge value relationships bring up the basics open to give , from " Chemistry " at school the students universal values with introduce to them ecological education and education to give

topics and departments integrative learning methodology with acquaintance , - lessons design , chemical experience transfer technique and methodology work exit and *another cases* .

Chemistry study _ methodology course and natural-mathematical preparation of sciences interdisciplinary connections the following cases done is increased :

natural sciences education in the system of chemistry study _ subject as instead , at school modern education to quality in reaching natural of sciences role open to give

school chemistry course content integrative character justification , his natural and mathematics sciences content with of integration main directions to determine education content greening and valeologization ways _ open giving , ecological and valeological cultured the student formation ;

them in class use basics with introduction ;

chemistry science developing in education interdisciplinary relationship integrative approach based on done increase methodology seeing output ;

chemical issues solve methodology with get to know

school chemistry course topics and departments problem-integrative learning methodology with acquaintance , lessons design , technique work exit and

Other cases interdisciplinary experiment transfer methods .

Chemistry teaching methodology course and humanitarian education sciences between interdisciplinary in communications done is increased .

developing chemistry teaching humanization and humanization , it cultural content with to fill issues with get to know

chemistry course content integrative character justification , his humanitarian sciences content with integration fields to determine

interdisciplinary connections based on chemistry teaching humanization method and tools , them in class use methodology with introduction ;

topic and departments integrative learning methodology with get to know

chemistry according to school course for fish hunting , lessons design , interdisciplinary experiment transfer for technique and methods work exit and *another cases .*

of integration educational function seeing exit endings we are methodical of sciences content to the teacher them done increase for infinite opportunities present that it will we emphasize . From this except them _ Create not just fundamental knowledge and generalized skills formation , perhaps them professional in the field problems solution to do in the activity apply also provides experience .

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